

HIMACHALI DEITIES AND THEIR ROLES IN HIMACHAL PRADESH: SOCIOLOGICAL INFLUENCE AND CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract

Himachal Pradesh is known as the “Land of Living Gods.” It is distinguished by its mystifying and fascinating tradition of worshipping local deities reflecting reverence to the celestial beings, nature and community bonds. They call Himachal “Dev Bhoomi” because every village is a home to several deities. Every village also has its territorially bound main deity and a priest (gur) who is a medium of that deity. The gur allows divine possession to take place in his body for which he enters an altered state of consciousness. Unlike the pan Indian Hindu pantheon, these deities and their gurs are a part of the everyday lives of the devotees who seek divine healing. These issues can be of varying nature, be it physical or mental health, career, familial or community related, weather or theft. Under this system the village unites and acts like a close know family which in turn fosters harmony. The role of Himachali Deities and its sociological and cultural significance is a realm largely unknown to outsiders. Staunch belief in Deity System plays a pivotal role in environmental regulation as well. Himachal Pradesh harbours around 329 documented sacred groves called Dev Vans. These are forest areas protected and reserved for their religious significance. Local communities unite to safeguard these groves against any malicious activity thereby allowing flora and fauna to flourish. The Devis and Devtas move around in their palanquin or rather which is beautifully adorned with the mask of Devi or Devta they represent. The congregation of palanquins and festivity is a sight to behold. Such processions spark cultural values in the onlookers as well. Ethnographic analysis and regional studies across different districts of Himachal reveal the Deity System (Divine Governance) as a coherent system of belief that is still practised by the villagers in the picturesque Himachal. It binds an individual to a community, ancestry and natural world. This perspective stands in contrasting to the modern-day practises which have led to hazardous climatic condition and moral crises.

Key Words: *Himachali Deities, Sociological Influence, Cultural Significance, Ritual and Deity Council*

INTRODUCTION

Ever dreamt of a place where mountains reach out for the sky, where rivers nurture life and where every idol carries a unique tale within? Its none other than the spectacular and bountiful Himachal Pradesh. The happiness and well being of a community lies in the preservation of its indigenous cultural tradition. The people of Himachal Pradesh have reasons to be proud of their cultural heritage which they have preserved for ages. An essential part of this heritage is the focus on native gods, lovingly referred to as the Devis and Devtas. In Himachal, deities are not merely objects of worship, they are an institution in themselves that govern every aspect of the life of devotees and the village alike. People consult the deities for everything, whether it is an individual matter or a dispute involving many people. The deities guide all activities including festivals, marriages and rituals. The deities of Himachal not only reside amongst their people they also communicate with them. This happens through a state of trance, locally known as *khel*. This state is invoked by rituals and the shaman (*gur*) is chosen by the deity to act as its medium. This requires the *gur* to be in a state of trance. This does not happen voluntarily and to everybody. Being a *gur* is not a choice that can be made by village folk. A *gur* is believed to have been chosen by the celestial beings to experience and perform a role that is the backbone of the deity system.

The local deity is considered to be the supreme leader of and the highest authority of the region he/she inhabits. People abide by the rules laid down by the deity. Communities believe that deep faith in the deity shall keep misfortunes at bay. Deities have their own councils comprising mainly of *kardar* (manager), *gur* (shaman), *bhandari* (storekeeper) and priest (*pujari*). The merger of religion, governance and ecology provides a stable community. The decision of the deities is considered to be final and the villagers take a stand for the decision even if it leads to postponing or modifying the government initiatives too. Most of the village congregations revolve around the worship of the local deity. Village fairs are characterised by carrying the palanquins of the deities through the village. Being a palanquin bearer for the deity is considered to be an honour. Participation in festivals like the Kullu Dussehra require travelling long distances in palanquins and it follows a social order. Kullu Dussehra is a congregation of hundreds of Devi -Devtas from most of the regions of the state. The positioning of the palanquins around the chariot (Rath) of Raghunathji is based on divine hierarchy. The hierarchical order is humbly accepted by all the deities as a signal of reverence to Raghunathji thereby spreading a message of discipline, unity and acceptance. The week-long celebration involves traditional dances like Naati which has been preserved by the

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simple hill folk as a traditional art form up to the present times. Folktale (katha) appears to be a cultural, universal and common aspect of primitive and complex societies alike. The folktales make is aware of the existing traditions as to how they started and what is their significance. They do form an integral part of our culture.

Devis and Devtas are believed to protect the ecology of their region. According to beliefs the deities inhabit the natural surrounding of the region. They are often associated with sacred mountains, lakes and rivers. Around 329 sacred groves (Dev Van) are found in Himachal which are maintained by the temple committee and no trespassing is allowed in these groves. Cutting down of even a single tree can not be carried out without their permission. Disobedience is considered to invoke wrath of deities. Such an influence plays a key role in controlling pollution, maintaining climate and allowing biodiversity to flourish. Through most of the things mentioned above, gur- the spokesperson of deity, the acceptance of rules laid down by the celestial beings, adherence to the regulations, respecting the hierarchical order, learning traditions through folktales, respecting the boundaries of the forest and collective participation in the activities help children imbibe cultural and moral values and also inculcates in them a sense of responsibility.

To a westernized and modern mindset this may not sound practical but we cannot ignore the experience that has been lived by millions of people across centuries. The deity system is an enchanted world of divine possession, celestial beings and communal harmony in Himachal. Creating an affinity with this belief system keeps intellectual scepticism away and make a devotee one with the deity. That is why the traditions are still alive and are cherished by the young and old alike.

HISTORICAL AND MYTHOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

Himachal Pradesh is a treasure trove of rich cultural heritage. The deity system is believed to have arisen from the earliest tribal groups inhabiting this region. The folklore has been passed down through generations. Most of the Devtas are considered to be incarnations of Shiva and Vishnu and Devis are considered to be manifestations of Shakti. Other deities are considered to have attained the state of Sages (Rishi), warriors by severe penance and extraordinary valour shown in times of adversity. For instance, Jamlu Devta of Malana is believed to be a form of Rishi Jamdagni who is regarded as one of the seven Vedic sages. Malana is considered to be world's oldest democracy. The people of the village have their own judicial system and every decision is made under the celestial guidance of Jamlu Devta. Vashisht Temple in Manali is dedicated to Sage Vashisht and is famous for hot water spring. The water

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from the spring is believed to cure skin infections and cure pain. Hadimba Temple at Dhungri, Manali is the patron goddess of Himachal and is believed to conquer malevolent forces and maintain a balance between good and evil. People have a close affinity with their deities and obey the norms laid down by them. A deep sense of reverence and faith is considered to be the driving force behind this association. Deities are believed to cure illnesses, ensure a good harvest, bless the devotees with wealth and be their guardians. Violation of any normal lead to natural disasters and misfortune. It is the prime faith of the people that the village deities are like common humans with sentiments, emotions and pride. Narratives reflect the stories of incarnations of Shiva or Vishnu and the immortalization of Sages and warriors. For instance, Banasur was a demon king who was a staunch devotee, Shiva. He is revered as a deity in parts of Kinnaur. He resisted influx of outsiders and maintained regional identity. There are tales that narrate that divine signs were felt when the celestial being chose the place for his permanent residence. A number of stories have been passed down the generations what might have happened in the past. Somehow with the advent of modern society a lot of social and political changes swept across the state and the deities too adapted to the changing scenario. Some had to settle for land grants and temple endowments while others were termed merely as superstitions under the Colonial Administration. However, the faith of people continued to exist and the deities persisted as powerful moral authorities. People still consult the deity for everything whether they face a problem or want to make an important decision. The festivities of deities' brim with vividness even today.

The deity system encompasses all, the village functions as a family, where people from all castes and clan are assigned particular tasks and they participate in the festivities. This acts as a symbolic anchor to keep the communities together. Children growing up in such an environment absorb moral and ethical values through a living tradition. The different manifestations and incarnations of gods show coexistence of pan Indian gods like Shiva, Vishnu and Durga, as well as saints, warriors, and serpent gods. Tribal lores and Puranic texts have enough tales to support the same. The lores of Narayan Nag and Hadimbamata resist strict orthodoxy and allowing communities to retain control over their spiritual identities.

As stated earlier these deities are considered to be living beings, they are present and they respond, they have sentiments and they are filled with emotions. The living medium for communication is the gur who is invoked ritually to deliver divine messages, settle disputes, predict harvest and warn against any calamity that might hit the region. Sometimes, the deity

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even scolds the villagers for not paying heed to the instructions given by them. To a modern westernized thought process this might seem not to have a logic but for the devotees it strengthens the bond between the people and their gods. The deity is considered to be the guardian (kshetrapal) of a defined area and even other deities are expected to respect his jurisdiction. With new challenges such as natural calamity, drought or legal conflict, devotees wait patiently for the next *gur* ritual for instructions and guidance. This clearly shows that tradition is a responsive force rooted in the life's realities of people.

RITUAL HEIRARCHY AND DEITY ADMINISTRATION

The realm of Himachalideities is ubiquitous yet it is mostly undiscovered. The local deity is considered to be the highest authority of its region. People abide by the norms laid down by the deity. Every deity in Himachal Pradesh operates within a well-defined administrative system that is no less than human governance but it is divine and spiritually protected. The administration is not simply religious. It is systematically organised with well defined roles, and responsibilities. All this ensures that the functioning of the temple is seamless. Deities have their own councils. At the core of this council is the *gur* who is the medium of the deity and his body is possessed by the deity in an altered state of consciousness. A *gur* connects the divine and material world. Then there is the priest (*pujari*) who performs daily rituals and maintains sanctity of the temple. Another key figure is the *kardar* (manager) who is responsible for managing all the tasks related to finances, offerings and other arrangements. It is the duty of the *kardar* to ensure that all the events of the temple are well organised and transparent. *Bhandari* is the storekeeper of the temple. Besides these key position holders is another important figure, the *Bajantri* or the temple musician who uses traditional musical instruments like the *nagaara*, *dhol*, *Karnal* and *Shehnai*. These instruments invoke a divine environment for everyone to immerse in it.

These positions are not hereditary. Instead, dream visitation by the divine, spiritual visions and unexplained illnesses determine the suitable candidate for these positions. Thereafter rituals are performed to confirm and the chosen individual is formally inducted into the committee. Will of the deity determines the eligibility to be a part of the temple administration. These roles are looked upon highly by the people, elevating even a commoner to a respectable position of a spiritual authority. This event out any gap and ensures inclusivity.

Another important feature of this system is the Devta Sabha (deity council) which consists of priests, *gur*, elders and functionaries. It is a quasi-judicial body that addresses village issues

and disputes. Often the judgement of the devtasabha is accepted readily as it is considered to be emerging from the divine. The activities of the deity are governed by a ritual calendar. During winters when most of the villages of Himachal Pradesh are isolated by snow, the deity enters a state of rest (shayan) and rituals are minimal. However major festivals like Dussehra, Shivratri and village fairs are conducted when weather is ambient. The larger festivals show a heightened level of organisation.

With the advent of technology, live broadcasts of festivals are possible which is proving to be very helpful in promoting deity culture. The coexistence of religion and technology illustrates resilience for upholding traditions and authority and flexibility to adapt to changes.

DEVTA RAJ: THEOCRATIC SOCIAL ORDER

In many parts of Himachal Pradesh especially Kullu Valley it is observed that deities are not merely objects of worship. They are actively involved in governing all aspects of life- social, cultural, moral, ecological, religious and even political. Deity is considered as chief authority and its decision is deemed final. This Devta Raj – Rule of the deity is not merely metaphorical. People have complete faith in the justice delivered by the divine. In case of any dispute, *gurans* answers their queries through trance divination and the people humbly accept the decision. The word of the deity is considered to be final. Villagers believe that the deity is omnipresent, observes everything and protects all the people who follow the norms. In matters related to new constructions, building roads or any other major development, people seek the opinion of the deity. If the deity does not agree to the project, stay be postponed, halted or modified. The decision is transparent and people obey it because it is considered to be the word of the divine.

From tree felling to modification in or around the temple- nothing can proceed without the consent of the deity. Such is the belief that evening political leaders and government officials bow down to seek both, blessings of the divine and public approval. Disobeying the deity's word may result in unexplained illness, natural disaster, poor harvest or any other form of spiritual punishment. The oral transmission of deity during trance is remembered and retold, so that the common public may understand and it is expected to be obeyed. The Devta Raj not only solves public matters but also issues like addiction, domestic violence and other matters of individual concern.

ECOLOGICAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL INFLUENCE

Gursas a medium have supported environmental conservation. Himachali deities are believed to protect the ecological and environmental influences as they are associated with the elements of nature such as forests, rivers, mountains and lakes. The continuity plays a pivotal role in maintaining ecology and environment. Certain deities are associated with forests. The forest areas is protected and regarded for their religious significance. Trees are believed to be abode of gods and spirits. It is believed they must be protected from human interference, trespassing or any other activity like felling of trees or collection of forest products. Folklores state that people who violate the rules face the wrath of deities. Sometimes the entire community has to suffer in the form of an epidemic or poor crop harvest. Hence the sacred groves of the Dev Vans must be protected. They form a part of the forest which is left untouched by the humans. These areas are presided over and protected by the deity. The sacred groves thus form a valuable gene pool where flora and fauna thrives. Sacred groves do not allow a single tree to be cut without the permission of the deity. Chandika Devi in Kinnaur is believed to be a sacred grove and entry of outsiders is prohibited. Therefore nature and natural resources are protected. Such a mode of conservation of gene pool in its natural habitat boosts biodiversity. Rituals are performed to keep the deity happy and this ensures good harvest and overall well being of the community. Rainfall is believed to be controlled by local deities in Shat and Kotla villages. If a single tree has to be cut down, villagers offer prayers and seek permission from the deity's *gur*. Inclusion of ritual like Sair and Bhojare not merely festivities, they are a way of expressing gratitude to the celestial beings. This creates a harmonious and proximal relation between the sacred, community and nature. Sacred water bodies are considered abide of serpent gods. (*Nag Devta*) and polluting them is believed to invoke wrath of gods.

Fear of the divine, in a way acts as a powerful cultural tool which ensures conservation of Natural resources, flourishing flora and fauna, a stable environment which leads to ambient climatic conditions. In a world where climatic disturbances are changing the face of the earth, such a belief system is silently working towards maintain the natural balance.

GENDER ROLES AND FEMININE DEITIES

Shakti is the pivotal force behind creation. Shakti encompasses wide range of emotions, from nurturing to wrathful. Feminine divine form or Shakti holds an equally respectable place in Himachal Pradesh. Manifestation of Shakti such as Hadimba Mata, Chandika Devi and Jogni Mata are seen as fierce protectors however they are equally nurturing as mothers. Female

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deities are powerful supreme beings and they are not second to any male god. In some regions of Himachal Pradesh the female deities are feared more than the male deities. People hold the female deities in high regard. The worship of Devi is deeply embedded in the hearts of devotees. The festivities of the goddesses involve participation of women in huge numbers. Ironically, while the female deities enjoy a highly revered place, the roles of women in the spiritual practises and deity administration are curtailed. Deity Administration includes men and women are deprived from the duty during menstruation and childbirth. Villagers are said to be protected by these powerful goddesses and their worship creates an essential cosmic balance. Female deities are a symbol of strength and resilience in all spheres of life. In Kullu and Chamba festivals like *Jatra* and *Bhunda* are organized to worship and evoke the goddess. Beautifully decorated palanquins adorned with mask of the deity are carried by men whereas the females sing traditional hymns to praise and invoke the goddess.

A society where formal religious leadership is male dominated, women serve as vessels of knowledge. They transmit oral legends, maintain rituals and carefully pass them to the next generation. While the temple administration is headed by the males, the worship of deities at home is mostly carried out by women. This represents that home is a space where females enjoy sacred power. Although limitations exist, but no system can function without the balance of feminine and masculine. The females offer a parallel support system in the society and the divine feminine belief empowers women.

CONTEMPORARY TRANSFORMATIONS AND CHALLENGES

The role of Himachali deities and its sociological and cultural significance is a realm that is largely unknown and inaccessible to the outsiders. It is a world where deity speaks through humans and nature is considered alive. It is not an easy task to delve into the deity system and understand sacred rituals and practices. It requires keen interest, willingness to learn and the consent of the deity to unfold the layers of this almost impenetrable realm. Today Himachali Deities are showcasing resilience. Spiritual Practices are reviving amidst resistance. Modernization, tourist influx and education are drifting people away from the traditions. Moving to cities in search of better employment opportunities has created a gap between youth and ancestral rituals. There is a dire need to bridge the gap. Technology, documentation, revival of traditional art forms are budding and it is essential to nurture them. Divine speaks through the *gur* against alcoholism, domestic violence and other societal vices, however strict resistance to such practices is the need of the hour. The deities are adapting to modern values while maintaining cultural authenticity. This adaptability makes the older and

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the younger generation walk hand in hand and it will be successfully passed on to the future generations.

Use of social media and technology to broadcast live rituals is a great step towards letting the world know about the traditional Himachali traditions and cultural ethics. People joining hands for temple restoration reflects the willingness to preserve the heritage for future generations. Participation of young generation in village festivals and a keen interest in festivities is commendable. However increased tourism interferes with religious sanctity because outsiders are unaware of the norms and traditions which they violate unknowingly. A proper village administration and restricted access to sacred spaces should be prompted. Other matters such as gender inclusion, caste participation are being debated upon. Such a transformation is not easy but it is actively negotiable.

CONCLUSION

The local deities of Himachal Pradesh are considered as living institutions that are rooted, magical and vivid. The Himachali deities offer a reactive reverence for nature and strengthens community bonds. Deities perform a role that is the backbone of the social system in Himachal Pradesh. Devis and Devtas of the valley are an integral part of the daily lives of people. Presence of a deity in a village influences the governance, puts an end to conflicts, conserved gene pool and provides a cultural identity to the inhabitants. In today's world where merger is resisted, Himachali Deity System displays a beautiful blend of faith, nature and community. The keen involvement of the villagers in rituals show that villagers are not merely followers but active guardians of divine laws. The verbal transmission of traditional knowledge, role of deity in revolving conflicts strength the values of deity system. With the world losing its cultural heritage, the Himachali Deity System strikes a fantastic balance between being authentic yet flexible. Modernization has influenced the lifestyle of people yet the have integrated spirituality in their changed lifestyle. Therefore Himachali Deity Acts as a symbolic anchor that keeps the communities together, promotes ethical governance and plays a role in creating harmony with nature.

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